

Adsorptive Properties of Synthetic Resins.

BY S. S. BEATNAGAR, A. N. KAPUR AND M. L. PURI.

Synthetic resins, as a rule, are not composed of single entities but consist of macromolecules of varying size and are usually classed as "xerogels". The term has been applied to such natural colloids as cotton, wool, silk, hair, horn and such artifacts as gelatin, leather, charcoal, cellulose derivatives and to completely synthetic products such as phenol-formaldehyde resins and silica gel (Sheppard, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1933, 29, 77).

Barthelemy (*Chim. et Ind.*, 1926, 16, 367) studied the behaviour of alcoholic suspensions of phenol-aldehyde resins under the influence of an electric field and observed that the alkaline-catalysed resins migrated to the cathode, while the acid catalysed ones to the anode. He regarded them therefore as ionic micelle. The growth of colloidal aggregates presumably occurs through the ionic nature of these particles. The sizes of the colloidal resin particles (Dubrisay, *Chim. et Ind.*, 1928, 666) range from the smallest, which can be detected by means of the ultramicroscope to the largest which are present in partial suspensions.

From the above evidence it is clear that synthetic resins possess colloiddally disperse structures with a strongly developed inner surface. It would have been natural, therefore, to look for pronounced adsorptive properties in them. It is surprising, however, that no one, until recently, investigated this field of research. Credit is due to Adams and Holmes (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1935, 54, 11) from Prof. Morgan's laboratories, who have studied the adsorption of a large number of cations from aqueous solutions of metallic salts by synthetic resins derived from polyhydric phenols and formaldehyde. They have observed considerable removal of antimony, bismuth, lead, mercury, silver, tin, vanadium, uranyl and methylene blue with one or other of the resins and came to the conclusion that these resins were generally superior to the recognised adsorbents like base exchange material and active carbon. The work of Adams and Holmes (*loc. cit.*) is that of pioneers in the field indicating new lines of investigation; their results, as they have themselves pointed out, are more or less qualitative and comparative in nature. It is obvious that this subject presents a most

interesting scope for colloid-chemical investigations not only of theoretical, but also of practical interest and it has, therefore, been considered desirable to undertake a detailed quantitative study of adsorption on these new adsorbents from the following standpoints:—

1. Method of activation.
2. Effect of natures of solvent on adsorption.
3. Adsorption of non-or weakly dissociated substances in aqueous solution.
4. Adsorption of strongly dissociated substances in aqueous solutions, *e.g.*, mineral acids and bases.

E X P E R I M E N T A L .

Preparation of Resins—Phenol (2 parts), formalin (40%, 4 parts) and water (25 parts) were refluxed over a sand-bath and concentrated hydrochloric acid (1 part) was added. A violent reaction took place and the resin separated within a couple of minutes. It was filtered off and washed first with dilute mineral acid, and finally with hot water until the filtrate was free from all traces of acid, phenol and formaldehyde. The resin was dried in an air-oven at 100-110°, powdered and passed through a 90 mesh sieve. The powdered resin was placed in a vacuum desiccator over soda lime and repeatedly evacuated, after which treatment the resin was ready for use. The resins on incineration gave no ash.

The experimental technique of adsorption measurement consisted in setting up a series of equal volumes of solution of differing and measured concentration, C_0 . Then, equal masses of the sorbent were placed in each solution. The systems were agitated for half an hour and allowed to remain until equilibrium was attained. After the sorbent had settled down, portions of the supernatant solution were analysed to determine the equilibrium concentration C_e . The amount of solute sorbed in each case was then taken to be $C_0 - C_e$. The amounts of adsorption, represented by x/m (expressed in milligram-equivalents per gram of adsorbent) in the tables are obviously not strictly accurate in as much as no attempt was made to correct for the adsorption of solvent. An error was undoubtedly introduced, but it must be very small as the solutions were very dilute and the adsorption of solvent would not materially alter the concentration,

Methods of Activation.—The effect of well known methods of activating adsorbents was studied on a recorsinol-formaldehyde resin and the results are given in Table I.

TABLE I.

Sorption from 50 c.c. 0.0753*N*-NaOH soln. by 0.5 g. of resin.

	Concentration.		Amount adsorbed <i>x</i> .	% sorption.	Increase in % sorption.
	Before sorption C ₀ .	After sorption C _∞ .			
Original resin	0.1507 g.	0.09305 g	0.05765 g _a	38.24	...
Resin steamed	0.1507	0.0856	0.0651	43.19	4.95
Resin treated with 5% HCl and washed till filtrate showed absence of Cl ⁻	0.1507	0.0846	0.0661	43.86	5.62
Resin heated at 140° under vacuum	0.1507	0.0921	0.0586	38.88	0.64
Resin evacuated for 2 hours	0.1507	0.0893	0.0614	40.74	2.50
Resin treated with NaOH and washed till the filtrate was neutral to litmus	0.1507	0.0912	0.0595	39.48	1.24

It is clear from the above table that the treatment with steam and 5% HCl increased the adsorptive capacity of the resin by about 5%. Though quantitative experiments were only tried for a solution of sodium hydroxide, it was noticed that the increase in adsorption was more or less general for all adsorbed materials.

Effect of the Nature of Solvent on Adsorption.—The sorption of a given solute by charcoal from a wide variety of solvents has been studied by various workers notably Freundlich (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1920, 73, 385), Lundelius (*Kolloid Z.*, 1920, 26, 145), Gurtvitsch (*Kolloid Z.*, 1623, 32, 80 ; 1926, 38, 247), Heymann and Boye (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1930, 180, 219) in an attempt to explain the different degrees of adsorption from different solvents. Explanations have been offered based on surface tension, solubility, heats of wetting and molecular polarisation. While no general rule could be given, it was concluded from the results obtained that a solute is apt to be weakly sorbed from solvents in which it is very soluble, from solvents

which wet the sorbent with high energy, and from solvents possessing weak dipole moments.

We have studied the sorption of benzoic acid from a number of solvents by a resorcinol-formaldehyde resin and the results are given in Table II.

TABLE II.

Sorption from 50 c. c. of 0.0163*N* benzoic acid soln. by 0.5 g. of resin in different solvents.

Solvent.	% Sorption.	Mol. polarisation, in cm ³ .	Dipole moment $M \times 10^{18}$ e.s.u.	Solubility of benzoic acid per 100 g. of the solvent at 25°.
CS ₂	20.54	21.3	0	4.571
Benzene	1.683	26.3	0 (0.2)	11.605
CCl ₄	13.87	28.1	0	3.965
MeOH	1.196	36.8	1.7 (1.15)	73.50
EtOH	1.819	52.1	1.7 (1.53)	57.70
Acetone	2.213	63.7	2.6 (1.28)	55.60
Water	51.26	70.1	1.85	0.345

The values for dipole moments and molecular polarisations have been taken from the table of dipole moments collected by Sidgwick (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1934, 30, 905). It is obvious from Table II that though no definite rule, inter-relating the amount absorbed of a solute in various solvents to its solubility in them or to the dipole moment of the solvent, can be given, fair guesses can be made. In developing a general theory, account must be taken not only of the influence of the solvent on adsorbate but also its influence on the adsorbent. The high adsorption from water is explained according to Freundlich ("Colloid and Capillary Chemistry," p. 192) who stated "Water is characterised by a high surface tension and by a high interfacial tension against other liquids. We may therefore ascribe to it also a high interfacial tension against solids, especially hydrophobic solids. On the other hand, adsorption is low from organic liquids such as benzene, alcohol, etc., in the case of which we may assume, for similar reasons, a low interfacial tension against solids." If the solubility of a given adsorbate is the same in a number of different solvents, greater

adsorption will occur from solutions, the solvent of which has higher interfacial tension against the adsorbent.

The difference in degree of sorption from different solvents may be used advantageously in the recovery of various substances from solutions. A dilute aqueous solution of a dye, like acridine orange can be readily and completely decolourised by the sorbent resin. If the resin is then placed in alcohol, from which acridine orange is sorbed less than from water, a large amount of it goes into solution in the alcohol. Further, it was observed that these resins showed a marked adsorptive capacity for alkaloid bases and this has been made use of in the extraction and purification of alkaloids. An aqueous solution of an alkaloid salt was treated with a sorbent resin and made slightly alkaline to liberate the alkaloid base which was strongly sorbed. The sorbent was removed and treated with an organic solvent which extracted a large part of the alkaloid. Quantitative experiments in this direction are being carried on and the results will be communicated in a later paper.

*Adsorption of Non- or Weakly dissociated Substances
in Aqueous Solution.*

The adsorption of aromatic and aliphatic acids from aqueous solutions has been studied and the results are given in Tables IIIa, IIIb and IV. Table IIIa gives the percentage sorptions of various organic acids from aqueous solutions by a resorcinol-acetaldehyde resin and shows the following general effects :—

(i) Sorption of aromatic acids is greater than the sorption of aliphatic acids.

(ii) The adsorption of organic substances from aqueous solutions increases strongly and regularly as we ascend the homologous series.

(iii) Substituents such as -OH and -NH₂ lower the sorptive affinity.

TABLE IIIa.

Sorption of various organic acids from 50 c. c. of 0.12N aqueous solution by 1 g. of resin.

Adsorbed substance.	% Sorption.	Adsorbed substance.	% Sorption.
Benzoic acid	55.80%	Formic acid	1.431
Salicylic acid	50.03	Acetic acid	3.527
Anthranilic acid	40.09	Propionic acid	10.012
Picric acid	13.87	Butyric acid	14.32
		Amino-acetic acid	0.50
		Lactic acid	7.14

TABLE III b.

Sorption of aromatic acids from 50 c.c. solution by 1 g. of resorcinol-acetaldehyde resin.

Benzoic acid		Salicylic acid		Picric acid	
C_e .	x/m .	C_e .	x/m .	C_e .	x/m .
0.01029	0.4155	0.010580	0.3415	0.013860	0.1181
0.00901	0.3955	0.008925	0.3420	0.010470	0.1050
0.00701	0.3675	0.007010	0.3101	0.008337	0.09572
0.00539	0.3400	0.005819	0.2913	0.006586	0.08570
0.00470	0.3106	0.005174	0.2653	0.005508	0.07952
0.00390	0.2930	0.004529	0.2391	0.004462	0.07228
0.00323	0.2647	0.003815	0.2099	0.002869	0.05917
0.00259	0.2357	0.003239	0.1874	0.001591	0.04174
0.00204	0.2096	0.002643	0.1618		

TABLE IV.

Sorption of fatty acids from 60 c.c. of aqueous solution by 1 g. of resorcinol-acetaldehyde resin.

Formic acid		Acetic acid		Propionic acid		Butyric acid	
C_e .	x/m .	C_e .	x/m .	C_e .	x/m .	C_e .	x/m .
0.06800	0.06100	0.09700	0.2320	0.0958	0.3790	0.0798	0.4260
0.05600	0.05100	0.08401	0.2065	0.0830	0.3610	0.0540	0.3575
0.04948	0.04304	0.07208	0.1810	0.06808	0.3414	0.03932	0.3116
0.04124	0.03522	0.06010	0.1500	0.05656	0.2927	0.03274	0.2617
0.03298	0.02869	0.04801	0.1240	0.04500	0.2498	0.02616	0.2113
0.02477	0.01956	0.03626	0.0770	0.03369	0.1914	0.01932	0.1767
0.01647	0.01434	0.02425	0.0460	0.02215	0.1460	0.01272	0.1275
0.008117	0.006581	0.01250	0.0090	0.01130	0.0582	0.006128	0.07771

Tables III b and IV show the variation of absorption with concentration of aromatic and aliphatic acids respectively. The results for the three aromatic acids show that at the highest concentrations the adsorptions are approaching the saturation values. Those for the aliphatic acid show that the saturation values are attained much more slowly in these cases.

Adsorption of Strongly Dissociated Substances in Aqueous Solution.

(a) *Adsorption of Inorganic Bases.*—The adsorption from aqueous solutions of the sodium hydroxide, potassium hydroxide, sodium carbonate and potassium carbonate of concentrations varying from 0.1*N* to 0.01*N* has been studied. All experiments were repeated a number of times. The data given in Table V are averages of at least four independent determinations. It will be noted that typical adsorption isotherms are obtained. This indicates that adsorption or surface reactions must predominate. It seems probable that in these systems "chemical reactions" may and probably do occur, but they are limited to the surface only; these reactions are, therefore, adsorptions of the "heteropolar" type which has been discussed by Freundlich ("Colloid and Capillary Chemistry," p. 287). With fairly dilute solutions used, there appears to be no reason to consider the process to be other than one of adsorption.

TABLE V.

Sorption of bases from 0.1*N*-aqueous solutions by 0.5 g. of resorcinol-formaldehyde resin.

Sodium hydroxide			Potassium hydroxide		
<i>C_e</i> .	<i>x</i> .	<i>x/m</i> .	<i>C_e</i> .	<i>x</i> .	<i>x/m</i> .
0.07630	2.370	4.740	0.07628	2.417	4.834
0.06655	2.345	4.690	0.06697	2.343	4.686
0.05722	2.277	4.554	0.05766	2.272	4.544
0.04744	2.225	4.450	0.04838	2.195	4.390
0.03862	2.137	4.274	0.03907	2.121	4.242
0.02970	2.030	4.060	0.03024	2.000	4.000
0.02185	1.814	3.628	0.02188	1.830	3.660
0.01348	1.652	3.304	0.01302	1.711	3.422
0.006024	1.397	2.794	0.006053	1.402	2.804
0.001375	0.8624	1.7248	0.001393	0.862	1.7248

TABLE V (contd.).

Sorption of bases from 0.1 N- aqueous solutions by 0.5 g. of resorcinol-formaldehyde resin.

Sodium carbonate			Potassium carbonate		
C_e .	x .	x/m .	C_e .	x .	x/m .
0.08880	1.0320	2.0640	0.08742	1.2120	2.4240
0.07956	0.9661	1.9322	0.07818	1.1380	2.2760
0.07021	0.9084	1.8168	0.06880	1.0810	2.1620
0.06091	0.8478	1.6956	0.05953	1.0140	2.0280
0.05164	0.7830	1.5660	0.05023	0.9493	1.8986
0.04234	0.7224	1.4448	0.04093	0.8826	1.7652
0.03258	0.7069	1.4138	0.03164	0.8160	1.6320
0.02326	0.6479	1.2958	0.02232	0.7537	1.5074
0.01441	0.5408	1.0816	0.01349	0.6406	1.2812
0.006506	0.3408	0.6816	0.006043	0.3913	0.7826

TABLE VI.

Sorption of aniline from 100 c.c. aqueous solution by 9.5 g. of resorcinol-formaldehyde resin.

C_e .	x .	x/m .	C_e .	x .	x/m .
0.1840	1.845	3.690	0.08768	1.348	2.696
0.1654	1.684	3.368	0.06890	1.191	2.382
0.1454	1.651	3.302	0.05065	1.000	2.000
0.1260	1.562	3.124	0.03200	0.8387	0.16774
0.1074	1.401	2.802	0.01523	0.04904	0.09808

It is clear from Table V that the hydroxides are adsorbed much more than the carbonates. The amount of adsorption of potassium hydroxide is practically the same as that of sodium hydroxide, while potassium carbonate is adsorbed to a greater extent than sodium carbonate.

Table VI shows the adsorption of aniline from aqueous solutions. It is obvious that the inorganic bases are adsorbed more than the organic bases.

(b) *Adsorption of Inorganic Acid.*—The adsorption of hydrochloric, sulphuric and nitric acids from aqueous solutions by an amino-resin has been studied and the results are shown in Table VII. The resin was prepared by condensing *m*-phenylenediamine (1 part), formaldehyde (2½ parts) and 50% hydrochloric acid (10 parts). The resin was dried in presence of hydrochloric acid and thoroughly washed with hot water to remove all impurities.

The results show that the inorganic acids are preferentially adsorbed in the order $H_2SO_4 > HNO_3 > HCl$. The adsorption of acids is, thus, influenced by their basicity and to a smaller degree by the nature of the anion.

TABLE VII.

Sorption of mineral acids from 0.05*N* aqueous solutions by 0.5 g. of *m*-phenylene diamine-formaldehyde resin.

Sulphuric acid			Nitric acid			Hydrochloric acid		
<i>C_e</i>	<i>x</i>	<i>x/m</i>	<i>C_e</i>	<i>x</i>	<i>x/m</i>	<i>C_e</i>	<i>x</i>	<i>x/m</i>
0.022020	1.2358	2.4716	0.03637	1.1070	2.2140	0.04077	1.002	2.0040
0.016614	1.1340	2.2680	0.02898	1.0010	2.0020	0.03232	0.9337	1.8674
0.011776	0.9980	1.9960	0.02159	0.8973	1.7946	0.02403	0.8565	1.7130
0.007388	0.8352	1.6704	0.01421	0.7914	1.5828	0.01658	0.7300	1.4600
0.003408	0.6480	1.2960	0.008097	0.6105	1.2210	0.009672	0.5689	1.1378
0.001163	0.3562	0.7124	0.002842	0.3782	0.7564	0.003452	0.3666	0.7332

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS.

1. Synthetic resins have been prepared which show marked general adsorption.

2. The taking up of dissolved substances from solution by the adsorbent resins followed the ordinary laws of adsorption and is mainly a surface phenomenon as log *x/m* and log *C_e* curves are straight lines and *x/m* and *C_e* curves are typical adsorption isotherms.

3. A solute is apt to be weakly sorbed from solvents in which it is very soluble and from solvents possessing weak dipole moments. If the solubility of a given adsorbate is the same in a number of different solvents, greater adsorption will occur from solutions, the solvent of which has higher interfacial tension against the adsorbent.

4. The difference in degree of sorption from solvents may be used advantageously in the recovery of various substances from solutions. •

5. Sorption of aromatic acids is greater than that of aliphatic acids.

6. In a homologous series, the adsorption of organic substances from aqueous solutions increases strongly and regularly as we ascend the series.

7. Effect of substituents on the sorptive affinity has been studied.

8. In the adsorption of inorganic bases, the hydroxides are adsorbed much more than the carbonates. The amount of adsorption of potassium hydroxide is practically the same as that of sodium hydroxide.

9. Inorganic acids are preferentially adsorbed in the order $H_2SO_4 > HNO_3 > HCl$.

10. The adsorptive resins resemble charcoal more than silica in their adsorptive properties. Silica adsorbs more from organic solutions than from aqueous solutions, while in the case of charcoal and the resins, it is quite the reverse. Further, whereas charcoal does not adsorb inorganic bases and silica inorganic acids, the adsorptive resins adsorb both types of substances fairly strongly.